

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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HOW INATURALIST OBSERVATIONS CONTRIBUTE TOWARDS ARACHNID DIVERSITY

The **iNaturalist observation database** is a vast collection of images contributed by nature enthusiasts worldwide. It is part of the **iNaturalist platform**, which allows users to record and share observations of plants, animals, fungi, and other organisms. Here's what makes it special:

- **Community-Driven:** Users upload photos of their observations, which are then identified and verified by experts and fellow naturalists.
- **Scientific Contribution:** The data are shared with biodiversity science repositories, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), to help researchers study species distribution and ecology.
- **Open Data Access:** Many of the images are licensed under **Creative Commons**, allowing for their use in scientific and educational purposes.
- **Database Integration:** Metadata associated with these images—such as location, date, and species identification—can be accessed and analysed using tools like **SQLite databases**.

So far, we have found that combining museum specimens sampled during SANSA surveys with iNaturalist observations provides a more comprehensive view of spider species diversity and their geographic range than one source alone. Several articles have already been published in the SANSA Newsletter 54. See also articles in this issue, pages 17 to 31.

The iNaturalist observations are making a very important contribution to species:

- Indicate new unrecorded species
- Add additional distributional records
- High light colour variations
- Provide additional information on lifestyles and behaviour

Unfortunately, there are some limitations to the full use of Naturalist observations

- Due to somatic similarity between species of several families and genera. Many species cannot be identified to species level from photographs alone.
- For a species to reach Research Grade on iNaturalist at least two persons need to confirm the identification. Due to a lack of specialist participation, species confirmation is frequently not available.
- To get spider species listed on a country's national list on the World Spider Catalog, information on genitalia must be provided therefore specimens must be collected.

However, for spider conservation in South Africa, where 30% of species are listed as Data Deficient additional distribution data is needed. Therefore, iNaturalist observations could provide important additional information on data deficient species.

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One of the projects on iNaturalist "Spiders of South Africa" was originated in November 2021 by Marie Delpont. To date 103 771 spider observations from 1223 species can be viewed. However a large number are still undetermined.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R., BOOYSEN R., VICKERS M.E., CHRISTIAAN R., STANDER A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2025. A little goes a long way: a rapid sampling protocol repeated seasonally generates considerable spider biodiversity data in an arid national park. *Biodiversity and Conservation* (2025) 34: 3453–3479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-025-03107-9>

ABSTRACT: The Richtersveld National Park (RNP) is situated in the extreme north-western part of South Africa and protects a large proportion of the Desert Biome in the country, as well as part of the globally significant Succulent Karoo Biome. Despite its extreme aridity and ecological significance, the spider fauna of the park is very poorly known. Prior to 2021, only 92 spider species had been recorded from the park, including some records represented in the primary taxonomic literature. However, some additional historical records represent misidentifications. To generate arachnid diversity data from RNP, we carried out sampling in four biotopes (open plain, riparian vegetation, east- and west-facing mountain slopes) using a standardized rapid sampling protocol (RSP) using vegetation beating and separate hand collecting in litter and from rocks. The RSP was repeated in mid-summer (January 2021) and winter (July 2021) to assess seasonal changes in arachnid assemblage composition. Here we only report on the spiders. In total, 2409 spiders were collected, representing 121 species and 32 families. Spider abundance and species richness were far higher in winter ($n = 1546$, $S = 110$) than in summer ($n = 863$, $S = 75$). Additional collecting at other sites by beating, litter sifting and hand collecting at night yielded 60 species in total, of which 13 species had not been recorded historically or using the RSP. Of the historically recorded species, 62 were not collected using the RSP or in the additional collecting samples. An updated checklist of the spider fauna of the RNP now includes 190 species in 37 families, more than doubling the historical records, and provides a useful foundation for conducting ecological research in the park. Furthermore, 191 specimens representing 120 species were successfully sequenced for a DNA barcoding project to aid future identification.

Two of the newly described species sampled from the region (Haddad, 2022).

Namundra murphyi Haddad, 2022

Platyooides robertsi Haddad, 2022

HADDAD C.R. 2022. Two new dionychnan spiders from arid western South Africa (Araneae: Prodidomidae, Trochanteriidae). *Arachnology* 19(Special Issue): 341–347. [doi:10.13156/ arac.2022.19.sp1.341](https://doi.org/10.13156/ arac.2022.19.sp1.341)

The Richtersveld National Park (RNP)

NEW PUBLICATIONS

YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T. & SCHOEMAN A.S.D. 2025. Survey of epigeic spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in a litchi orchard in Mpumalanga, South Africa. *Koedoe* 67(1): 51. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koeoe.v67i1.1851>

ABSTRACT: Spiders were sampled using pitfall traps over two 21-day periods in July 2020 and November 2020 at five sites within a litchi orchard in Hazyview, located in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa. In total, 407 specimens representing 16 families, 25 genera and 30 species were recorded. The Corinnidae (n = 229) represented 56.3% of all spiders collected, followed by the Salticidae (n = 56, 13.8%), Lycosidae (n = 40, 9.8%) and Gallieniellidae (n = 24, 6.0%). The families with the highest number of species were Salticidae (n = 7) and Lycosidae (n = 4). Wandering spiders made up 93.3% of the total specimens collected, while web-building spiders accounted for only 6.7%.

The most abundant species was a Corinnidae, *Copa flavoplumosa* (n = 229, 56.3%). Credit: Peter Webb

Although this study focused on epigeic spiders rather than foliage spiders, some ground-dwelling species can help reduce pest populations through their vertical movement within the orchard. Therefore, understanding the assemblages and dominant patterns of spiders found on the floor of the litchi orchard can inform our advocacy for reducing chemical use and increasing the reliance on spiders for biological pest control. Additionally, recognising these dominant patterns is essential for maintaining suitable habitat conditions, ensuring the sustainability of biological control programmes and the conservation of predator species.

Followed by the Salticidae, *Baryphas ahenus* (n = 41, 10.1%). Credit: Peter Webb

NEW PUBLICATIONS

YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T., SIMBA V & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2025. Preliminary survey of epigeic spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in macadamia orchards of Mpumalanga province in South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 63 (6) <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.70086>

ABSTRACT: Our current knowledge of spider diversity in macadamia orchards in Mpumalanga province, South Africa is based on plant-dwellers. Thus, this study determined species abundance and richness of ground-dwelling spiders in macadamia orchards in Mpumalanga. We collected 845 specimens in 21 families, 43 genera and 57 species. The most species-rich and abundant families were the Lycosidae, Salticidae and Gnaphosidae. *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903, *Proevippa fascicularis* Purcell, 1903, *Drassodes solitarius* Purcell, 1907, *Zelotes tuckeri* Roewer, 1951 and *Nomisia transvaalica* Dalmas, 1921 were the most abundant species. This study increased the number of species recorded from macadamia orchards from Mpumalanga to 134.

Pardosa crassipalpis Purcell, 1903 one of the most abundant species (new name *Spiniculosa crassipalpis* see p. 5) Credit: Vida vd Walt

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R, CODRON D. & BOOYSEN R. 2025. Identifying the substrate and vegetation characteristics driving population densities in the buckspoor spider, *Seothyra schreineri*. *African Journal of Ecology* 2025; 63:e70074 8 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.70074>

ABSTRACT: Buckspoor spiders (Araneae: Eresidae: *Seothyra* Purcell) are a distinct lineage of burrow-inhabiting web-building spiders endemic to the arid and semi-arid parts of southern Africa. We investigated the role of substrate and vegetation characteristics on site selection in *Seothyra schreineri* Purcell in the xeric Nama Karoo of the western Free State Province, South Africa. We studied web densities in two 0.5 ha plots in an open habitat grazed by sheep and found declining web densities with increasing distance from the border fence. Web densities in the 1 m² plots were negatively correlated with increasing grass density, positively correlated with increasing percentage fine gravel, whereas shrub cover, litter, hard soil and stones had a very weak effect. Our results indicate that the spatial distribution of fine gravel in Nama Karoo landscapes is a key factor determining the occurrence of *S. schreineri*, a finding that can guide future sampling efforts, leading to a more complete prediction of the species' distribution and, ultimately, its overall conservation status.

FIGURE 1. *Seothyra schreineri* and its habitat on the farm Bankfontein: (a) Adult male, a mimic of *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants; (b) Non-mimetic burrow-bound female; (c) Close-up view of four-lobed web; (d) Cluster of three webs: Left and right webs with four lobes, middle web with three lobes; (e) Landscape view of the Nama Karoo habitat; (f) Detail of the substrate, indicating grass (g), gravel (gr), hard soil (h), karoo shrubs and bushes (b), plant litter (l) and stones (s).

HAVE YOU SEEN ANYTHING LIKE THIS??

Under a rock in the Swartberg Mountains, we found eight tiny 'nest balls', each no bigger than a peppercorn, made from precisely cut pieces of restio stems. They were found in a half-moon shaped, silk-lined cavity and closely mimic the restio seeds scattered in the surrounding fynbos. At this site, a spider from the family Theridiidae, smaller than a single ball, was present. In two further cases of similar nests, spiders belonging to the genus *Palpimanus* were sighted. The purpose of these remarkable constructions remains unknown. If you have come across anything like this, or can share further info, please contact us.

Karin and Collette,
at wildbees.co.za@gmail.com or collettehurt@gmail.com.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

KRONESTEDT T. 2025. *Spiniculosa*, a new wolf spider genus (Araneae, Lycosidae) from Africa, with description of a new species from the coast of Kenya. *Zootaxa* 5666 (2): 211–224.

ABSTRACT: *Spiniculosa* gen. nov. is proposed for two wolf spider species from the Afrotropical Region. One of them was formerly placed in the genus *Pardosa*, viz. *Spiniculosa crassipalpis* (Purcell) comb. nov., while the other, *S. albida* sp. nov., is newly described. These species share traits in the morphology of the male copulatory organs, as well as the males having a row of short spine-like setae proventrally on the first leg coxa and trochanter respectively. *Spiniculosa crassipalpis* (South Africa, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, DR Congo, Tanzania, Kenya and Ethiopia) is redescribed and illustrated, the male palp illustrated for the first time. It is here synonymized with *Pardosa upembensis* (Roewer, 1959) syn. nov. *Spiniculosa albida* sp. nov., remarkable for its whitish body coloration, is described on material from a seashore with white sand in Kenya.

FIGURE 1. Habitus (in ethanol), dorsal view.—A–F. *Spiniculosa crassipalpis* (Purcell). A (m) from South Africa: Rust de Winter, B (f) from South Africa: Kameelfontein, C (m) and D (f) from Kenya: Lake Nakuru, E (m) and F (f) from Kenya: Tiwi Beach.

HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2025. A revision of the genus *Trachelas* L. Koch, 1872 (Araneae: Trachelidae) in the continental Afrotropical Region. *Zootaxa*, 5673 (4): 451–493. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5673.4.1>

ABSTRACT: The polyphyletic spider genus *Trachelas* L. Koch, 1872, with the type species *T. minor* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872 from Europe (also known in North Africa and Central Asia), has a worldwide distribution in the tropical, subtropical and temperate regions, although *Trachelas sensu stricto* is restricted to the Old World. Here the continental Afrotropical species are revised and a description of *Trachelas sensu stricto* is provided. *Trachelas canariensis* Wunderlich, 1987, *T. chubbi* Lessert, 1921, *T. pusillus* Lessert, 1923 and *T. sylvae* Caporiacco, 1949 are redescribed, and the female of *T. pusillus* described for the first time. Seven new species are described: *T. falsus* sp. nov. (m f, Côte d'Ivoire, Nigeria, South Africa and Tanzania), *T. humus* sp. nov. (m f, Namibia and South Africa), *T. leggi* sp. nov. (m f, South Africa), *T. longinquus* sp. nov. (m, Central African Republic), *T. russellsmithi* sp. nov. (f, Ethiopia), *T. scutatus* sp. nov. (m f, Ghana and Nigeria) and *T. smithi* sp. nov. (f, Kenya). The female of *Trachelas scopulifer* Simon, 1896 is redescribed, its male is described for the first time, and its transfer to *Thysanina* Simon, 1910 proposed. The immature female type of *T. punctatus* Simon, 1886 from Senegal is presumed lost and this species is considered a **nomen dubium**. A key to the continental species of Afrotropical *Trachelas* is provided. A molecular phylogeny based on the cytochrome oxidase subunit I gene (COI) indicates that the New World species of the genus belong to a distinct lineage and are only distantly related to *Trachelas sensu stricto*.

Trachelas canariensis, males from Bloemfontein (A) and Pretoria (B)

Distribution of *Trachelas canariensis* (yellow circles) and *T. chubbi* (blue circles) in the continental Afrotropical region.

NEW PUBLICATION

SALTICIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA
New release - part 3 now available

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V. HAD-DAD, C.R. FOORD S.H. ‡ & LOTZ L.N. 2025. The Salticidae of South Africa Part 3 (He-Iran). *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Version 1: 1-74*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17103454>

The family Salticidae is the largest spider family known from 689 genera and 6809 species. From South Africa 85 genera and 363 species are known (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The Salticidae Guides are arranged into seven volumes. The first two parts have been released earlier this year. Part 3 dealing with the genera *Heliophanus* to *Iranattus* are now available.

- *HELAFRICANUS* Wesolowska, 1986 (14 spp.)
- *HELIOCAPENSIS* Wesolowska, 1986 (12 spp.)
- *HELIOPHANUS* C.L. Koch, 1833 (9 spp.)
- *HISPO* Simon, 1886 (1 sp.)
- *HOLCOLAETIS* Simon, 1886 (2 spp.)
- *HOMALATTUS* White, 1841 (3 spp.)
- *HYLLUS* C.L. Koch, 1846 (5 spp.)
- *ICIUS* Simon, 1876 (6 spp.)

NEWS FLASH

CONGRATULATION RUAN BOOYSEN WITH YOUR PHD!

Revision and molecular phylogeny of the spitting spiders (Araneae: Scytodidae) of southern Africa

Scytodidae is a diverse group of spiders that has a worldwide distribution with a few synanthropic species. In southern Africa, only *Scytodes* has been recorded, with 36 species originally described from South Africa and Namibia. This study used morphological and genetic data from three gene regions, COI, H3 and 18S, to revise the genus *Scytodes* in southern Africa. Additionally, morphological analyses were used to evaluate the similarities between the species. Spiders were collected from all over South Africa and obtained from various national and international collections to uncover the diversity of this group. Additionally, 36 type-specimens from 27 species were examined physically or photographically. This study resulted in the description of 38 new *Scytodes* species and updated the descriptions for 27 existing species (out of 34 originally recorded from southern Africa), of which the male of *S. maritima* Lawrence, 1938 and the female of *S. elizabethae* Purcell, 1904 were described for the first time. Additionally, *S. quinqu* Lawrence, 1927 syn. nov. is here considered a junior synonym of *S. broomi* Pocock, 1902. *Scytodes constellata* Lawrence, 1938 is still considered *nomen dubium* until more data becomes available. Molecular analyses were not successful in sequencing the COI region (4/45 isolates) but had better success with 18S and H3 regions (35/45 and 38/45 isolates). This data was not sufficient for constructing a robust molecular phylogeny of the *Scytodes* of southern Africa, but 11 species groups were proposed using a similarity matrix based on Gower distances. Red List data for all species included in this manuscript were also provided.

Scytodes caffra

Scytodes elizabethae

Scytodes maritima

Scytodes arenaeus

24th Congress of the Entomological Society of Southern Africa

8 – 11 July 2025 | University of the Free State, Bloemfontein

The 24th ESSA Congress, was held at the University of the Free State, Bloemfontein campus, from 8–11 July 2025. Although most presentations focused on insects, it was interesting to note that several research projects also incorporate spiders into their findings. When the abstracts were searched for “spiders” it resulted in listing 15 talks from 7 universities. This include the talk of the keynote speaker Dr Pedro Cardoso who has previously worked with the late Prof Stefan Foord.

Keynote speaker: Dr. Pedro Cardoso

Pedro Cardoso is a researcher at CE3C within the Faculty of Sciences at the University of Lisbon. As the head of the Laboratory for Integrative Biodiversity Research (LIBRe), his primary focus is on understanding the global drivers of species extinction and the spatial and

temporal distribution of species and communities. To achieve these goals, his team is developing innovative statistical and computational tools to assess extinction risk and quantify biodiversity across taxonomic, phylogenetic, and functional dimensions. Using spiders and insects as model organisms, they are pioneering automated methods to evaluate species' exposure to threats and predict how these species may be impacted based on their unique traits.

• **University of the Free State**

Hannelene Badenhorst, Charles Haddad, Charlene Janion-Scheepers. Springtail and spider assemblages along an east-west environmental gradient in central South Africa.

Ruan Booysen, Charles Haddad. Revision and molecular phylogeny of the spitting spiders (Araneae: Scytodidae) of southern Africa.

Charles Haddad, Robin Lyle. A revision of the continental species of the genus *Trachelas* L. Koch, 1872 (Araneae: Trachelidae) in the Afrotropical Region.

• **University of KwaZulu-Natal**

Asande Hadebe, Sindiso Nkuna, Rob Slotow, Caswell Munyai. Longitudinal and lateral gradient influence on ant and spider biodiversity.

Thembeke Nxele, Taro Mwabvu, Manqoba Zungu. Soil arthropods in macadamia orchards: a case study in the Ray Nkonyeni Local Municipality, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa

Caroline Kunene, Caswell Munyai, Tom Bishop. Arthropod diversity along the Waterberg Mountains, Limpopo, South Africa.

Delegates at the 24th ESSA Congress

Zabentungwa Hlongwane, Thinandavha Munyai, Olwethu Majola, Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman, Georgette Legendijk. Diversity, composition, and distribution patterns of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in sand forest, South Africa.

• **University of Mpumalanga**

Happiness Madonsela, Tarombera Mwabvu, Inam Yekwayo. Surface-active arthropod assemblages in avocado orchards and savannah vegetation, Mpumalanga.

• **University of the Stellenbosch**

James Pryke, Megan Crowhurst, Charlene Janion-Scheepers, René Gagher, Colleen Seymour. Insect conservation in South Africa, in the age of insect declines: an overview of arthropod conservation research for the past 25 years and future considerations.

Juliette Chassain, John S. Terblanche, Charlene Janion-Scheepers. Soil biodiversity and soil food webs in sugarcane fields of southern Africa.

Abbygale Nel, René Gagher, James Pryke. Arthropod diversity as an indicator of disturbance impacts in the Southern Mistbelt Forests.

• **KwaZulu-Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg**

Mandisa Ndelela, Thembeke Nxele, Taro Mwabvu, Manqoba Zungu Soil arthropods in macadamia orchards: a case study in the Ray Nkonyeni Local Municipality, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

There was also a talk on Pseudoscorpiones by Jan Andries Neethling of the National Museum Bloemfontein, Bloemfontein, South Africa
Slow and steady - revising the taxonomy of South Africa's pseudoscorpions.

REVISITING SOME NATIONAL BOTANICAL GARDENS IN SOUTH AFRICA

Astri Leroy and John Leroy (info@spiders.co.za) The Spider Club of Southern Africa

The formation of the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) in September 2004 through the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEMBA) proclamation provided the ideal opportunity to showcase the biological diversity held within South Africa's 11 national botanical gardens. For years, the focus has been on the flora alone, but now faunal diversity is also receiving attention. These gardens are typically located in urban areas and constitute a significant proportion of "green space," holding primary conservation value for invertebrates. Spider surveys have been undertaken in several of the gardens.

The peri-urban Free State National Botanical Gardens in Bloemfontein was sampled by staff and students from the University of the Free State and the National Museum in Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). In the Western Cape, the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden was surveyed by the Universities of Stellenbosch and Cape Town (Pryke & Samways, 2009), and a final checklist was published by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2023). In Gauteng, an annotated list of spider species known from the Pretoria National Botanical Garden was published by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2024).

Throughout the years, John and I have had an interest in the arachnids of the national botanical gardens. We have sampled in the Lowveld National Botanical garden in Mbombela (previously Nelspruit) and the Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden in the west of Johannesburg. For the Lowveld garden we have a checklist in preparation.

Presently we are sampling in the Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (WSNBSG). The purpose of this study is to document the number of spider species present in the Garden, to determine species diversity, and to observe population shifts since 1991. A checklist of the spiders of the WSNBSG will be published and a SANBI booklet is envisaged using the photographs taken along with a short explanatory text. Presently we already have a list of 95 species from 37 families.

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The Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden and the spider survey.
Credits: Astri Leroy

MITEY MAGGIE TO THE WORLD

Ms Maggie Madijo Manyatsa, a Senior Research Assistant, works in the Arachnology Unit, Biosystematics, of the ARC-Plant Health and Protection and is currently managing the National Collection of Acari (Mites) (NCA). It is a National Public Goods Asset (NPGA) that Maggie has been solely responsible for since 2019, when all the researchers working on this collection left the organisation. Prof Eddie Ueckermann, a retired Acarologist from the ARC is currently training Maggie in Acari taxonomy, and he suggested that she attend the Acarology Summer Programme, which will be greatly beneficial to improve her skills as the collection manager of the mite collection and to develop a scarce skill within the ARC.

Through the National Department of Agriculture (DoA) Service Level Agreement (SLA), Maggie was able to attend the Programme at the University of Arkansas, focusing on Agricultural Acarology. It has helped to increase her knowledge and understanding of mites and the management of the NCA. She learned skills from basic mite slide preparation to the specialised mounting for groups like Eriophyoidea, a superfamily of extremely tiny, plant-feeding mites and males of the other mite groups. More importantly, she further improved her knowledge and understanding of the taxonomy of mites. This is currently a scarce skill in South Africa, as the researchers who were able to identify mites have retired or left the country.

Through attending the Programme, Maggie forged strong working relationships and built her scientific reputation with specialists and corporate scientists from around the world who work on mites. This can lead to future collaborations, funding opportunities for research and training opportunities. Maggie also arranged for 3D printed mites to be provided to the ARC. This is a game-changer for displays and outreach, since usually a compound microscope is needed to see these microscopic organisms.

The NCA, as part of the NPGA, is well known worldwide, and it is the largest mite collection in Africa. She discovered that Acarologists outside South Africa were unsure whether the collection was still active or who to contact for direct access, and Maggie was able to share her ARC contact details. The NCA gained a spotlight during the Programme, as some of the teaching material that was used during the course was slide-mounted mites from the South African NCA. There is a clear need for the NCA to become more active, visible, and for data to be made available to researchers in the acarology community, pest control companies, farmers, and other industrial businesses. Within the ARC, the need to increase the Arachnology unit through marketing of this collection has been identified, and a plan of action to address this is being developed. Exposure of the collection will inspire use of the collection, and Maggie, with the support from the Acarologists she met at the course to assist her with these tasks, as well as the help of Prof Eddie Ueckermann and Dr Davina Saccaggi, here in South Africa she is well underway to give the collection life again.

Maggie with the delegates that attended the Acarology Summer Programme at the University of Arkansas.

NEW SOUTH AFRICAN PUBLICATIONS

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2025. Review of the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) as prey of the mud-dauber wasps in Gauteng and Limpopo. *SANSA Newsletter* 54: 26–29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15753804>

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CELEBRATING 50 YEARS OF THE SPIDER CLUB

On 3rd August we had a lovely social day outside in the warm Pretoria sun to celebrate 50 years of the Spider Club of Southern Africa. Only two of the original members, John and Astri Leroy were able to be there, sadly the other two, Ansie and Nico Dippenaar were unable to attend.

Jarrold Todd (the Spider Club's Gauteng events organizer) and Robin Lyle of the ARC hosted the several dozen club members who did attend. Jarrold introduced Robin to those who didn't already know her and, using a pull down screen she showed some of the basics of arachnology to the audience. The pull down screen is a lovely tool! She also took everyone through the National Collection of Arachnida and explained its importance to science.

We had a spider walk in the veld, although at this time of year spiders are quite hard to find and Astri gave a brief history of how the club began. Jarrold and his fiancée Bianca made boerrie rolls with chakalaka and other kinds of relish, washed down with cooldrinks and Astri brought an awesome celebratory cake with edible decorations including all the spiders. After lunch Jarrold gave a quick course in macro photography, demonstrating the kind of photographic equipment that is necessary and how to use it. As always it is wonderful to be with a crowd of like-minded people and we had a really fantastic day.

A similar event took place at Kloovenberg Wine & Olive Estate near Riebeeck Kasteel in the Western Cape on 24th of May hosted by Wessel Pretorius and another event is planned for Bloemfontein toward the end of the year.

Astri and John with the CAKE at the National Collection of Arachnida in Pretoria.
Credit: Robin Lyle

First record of *Tibitanus sexlineatus* Simon, 1907 (Araneae: Philodromidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: The genus *Tibitanus* has been recognised for the first time from South Africa from photographs. The specimen with its reddish setae forming six parallel lines over the body resembles the species *T. sexlineatus* Simon, 1907, previously recorded from Guinea-Bissau.

INTRODUCTION

Simon (1907) described the female of the genus *Tibitanus* with *T. sexlineatus* as the type species from Bolama in Guinea-Bissau, but without illustrations. *Tibitanus* resemble *Tibellus*, to which it is related, but it differs by the anterior eyes being nearly equal; the median eyes being more than three times farther apart from each other than from the lateral ones; a much narrower clypeus; long, spiniform setae present on the anterior margin; serially arranged setae on the legs; leg IV clearly shorter than leg II. From *Suemus* it differs primarily in the legs, which, as in *Tibellus*, are spiny, and the anterior metatarsi are not much shorter than the tibiae.

Lessert (1928) had reservations about *Tibitanus*. He felt the diagnostic traits of *Tibitanus* overlapped significantly with those of *Tibellus*, especially in terms of body shape, eye arrangement, and leg proportions. He felt that the differences were more likely to be intraspecific variation or adaptations rather than genus-level distinctions. However, he conceded it might still be useful as a subgenus.

Millot (1942) examined a subadult female of *T. sexlineatus* from Kindia, Guinea, and provided the first image of the body (see Fig. 6), but also listed it as a subgenus. Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994), in their revision of *Tibellus*, clearly state that it is not a member of *Tibellus*. It is also presently listed on the World Spider Catalog (2025) as a distinct genus.

Tibitanus sexlineatus was first recognised from South Africa, based on an entry in the iNaturalist data set. A female was photographed (Figs 1-5) from the Blyde River floodplain, near Hoedspruit (-24.406, 30.814) on 21 January 2022 by Wynand Uys. The spider can be recognised by the longitudinal lines formed by reddish setae present on the carapace and abdomen (Figs 1, 2 & 5). Carapace is yellowish-brown, dorsally densely covered with yellowish-white setae, with reddish setae forming six parallel lines; white, rod-shaped, blunt setae are present in the eye region (Fig. 4). Abdomen decorated with the same reddish lines (Fig. 3); it is anteriorly obtusely truncated and slightly notched and posteriorly rounded; ventrally entirely covered with white setae. Legs are the same colour as the body, but decorated with spots.

A second species *T. nomas* Simon, 1910 was described from Namibia. It differs from *T. sexlineatus* by having a shorter cephalothorax lacking red setae, and the abdomen is not marked with red lines, and the genital area is pitted and keeled.

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Figures 1–6. *Tibitanus sexlineatus* female. 1–5. A female was photographed from the Blyde River floodplain, near Hoedspruit by Wynand Uys. 6. Line drawing after Millot (1942).

The first record of *Austrodomus gamsberg* (Araneae: Prodidomidae) from South Africa

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INTRODUCTION

The Prodidomidae is a small spider family, with only 196 species in 24 genera globally (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The family is particularly rich in South Africa, with six genera and 29 species having been recorded thus far (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). The Afrotropical fauna of the subfamily Prodidominae (excluding *Theuma* Simon, 1893 and *Prodidomus* Hentz, 1847) was revised by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020), with five genera revised and three new genera described. As part of that study, two South African species of *Austrodomus* Lawrence, 1947 were redescribed, *A. scaber* (Purcell, 1904) and *A. zuluensis* Lawrence, 1947, and *A. gamsberg* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020 was described from Namibia.

In March 2023, the University of the Free State held their annual field excursion at the Witsand Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape for the first time. This sampling effort greatly improved knowledge of arachnid biodiversity in the 2822 degree-square grid, which was one of the historically undersampled parts of the country (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Van der Mescht *et al.*, 2024). Among the many species recorded from the reserve for the first time was a single male specimen of *A. gamsberg*, representing the first record of the species from South Africa. Here we present images of the specimen, which was also successfully sequenced for the DNA barcoding gene (cytochrome oxidase subunit I, COI). This sequence is available on the SPIZA project on the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD, www.boldsystems.org).

Austrodomus gamsberg Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Figures 1–3

General habitus of male as in Fig. 1; small spider, 2.32 mm in total length, with bright yellow carapace and legs; abdomen creamy-yellow dorsally and ventrally. Palp as in Figs 2 and 3; ventral RTA blunt and subrectangular in lateral view, dorsal RTA short and broad, with blunt, ventrally directed tip; embolus almost transverse, with median swelling on outer surface.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Witsand Nature Reserve, Viewing Point, -28.5831, 22.4832, 1225 m a.s.l., 24.III.2023, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booyesen (under rocks, rocky hillside), 1m (NMBA 18624).

DNA Barcode: SPIZA1481-23.

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FIGURES 1–3. *Austrodomus gamsberg*, male. 1. Dorsal habitus; 2. Palp, ventral view; 3. Palp, retrolateral view.

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Philodromus otjimbombe (Araneae: Philodromidae), a Namibian species newly recorded and widespread in western South Africa

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INTRODUCTION

The Philodromidae remains very poorly studied in the Afrotropical Region, with only *Tibellus* Simon, 1875 having been revised to date (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994). Most of the described species of the other genera are poorly studied taxonomically and identification relies on outdated descriptions and generally poor illustrations, which is challenging. Currently, 34 species in six genera have been recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), although many more undescribed species have been distinguished but await description.

As part of a survey of the Succulent Karoo and Desert biomes along the western interior of the Northern Cape, South Africa, five degree-square grids were sampled in summer (January 2021) using a standardized sampling protocol, with the protocol repeated during winter (June-July 2021) in the Richtersveld National Park only (Haddad *et al.*, 2025). Philodromidae was one of the dominant groups of foliage-dwelling spiders sampled at all five sites, with one particular species particularly widespread.

As few philodromid species have been reported from western South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), identifying this material to species level proved very challenging. Although Simon (1910) described three philodromid species from the Namaqualand Region (Haddad & Marusik, 2019), none were illustrated and only *Tibellus australis* (Simon, 1910) has been subsequently redescribed (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994); *Philodromus vulpio* Simon, 1910 and *Thanatus namaquensis* Simon, 1910 still cannot be reliably identified. After studying numerous papers by Reginald Lawrence on the arachnid fauna of Namibia, it is clear that the dominant foliage-dwelling philodromid from western South Africa had an epigynal morphology consistent with *Philodromus otjimbombe* Lawrence, 1927, described from Otjimbombe at the Kunene River in northern Namibia (Lawrence, 1927).

In this paper, *P. otjimbombe* is illustrated, new records of the species from South Africa are presented, as well as a preliminary phylogeny of South African Philodromidae based on cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences, including several specimens of *O. otjimbombe* collected in western South Africa.

Philodromus otjimbombe Lawrence, 1927

Figures 1–13

General habitus of female as in Figs 1–3, of male as in Figs 4–6; small spiders, 2.24–3.66 mm in total length, with creamy-yellow to yellow-brown carapace with broad dark brown stripes laterally and broad white V-shaped marking behind posterior eye row; abdomen white to creamy-brown dorsally and ventrally, with light brown mottling and dark brown heart mark, oblique lateral markings near midpoint, and paired mediolateral chevron markings in posterior half. Legs same colour as carapace, all segments with faint bands, spine bases with black spots; legs relatively longer in males than females.

These two spiders resemble *Philodromus otjimbombe*. The photographs were taken by Cecile Roux in the Namakwa District Municipality, Northern Cape (-28.62, 19.50 and -30.11, 17.59). It was exported on 24 September 2025 from <https://www.innaturalist.org>.

Epigyne as in Figs 7–10; atrium with oblique sclerotized atrial margins, somewhat variable in shape, diverging posteriorly; spermathecae round, touching medially, located posteriorly in epigyne. Male palp as in Figs 11–13; ventral RTA shorter than dorsal RTA in lateral view, dorsal RTA slender, with disto-retrolaterally directed tip; tegulum oval, sperm duct with multiple loops; embolus originating at ca. 10 o'clock, curving around distal margin of tegulum, tip at ca. 1 o'clock.

FIGURES 1–13. *Philodromus otjimbube*, female (1–3, 7–10) and male (4–6, 11–13). 1–6. Dorsal habitus, showing variation in markings; 7–10. Epigynes, ventral view, showing variation in shape of atrial margins; 11, 12. Palp, ventral view; 13. Palp, retrolateral view. Credits: 1–6, 8–13. Charles Haddad; 7. From Law-

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Calvinia, Akkerendam Nature Reserve, 31°26.408'S, 19°46.651'E, 1060 m a.s.l., 16.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & A. Stander (beating shrubs, open plain), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/880); Calvinia, Donkieshoek Guest House, 31°27.475'S, 19°47.518'E, 995 m a.s.l., 18.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booysen (hand collecting, in house and garden), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/111); Meerkat National Park, Jaskloof, riparian woodland, 30°46.266'S, 21°14.982'E, 1135 m a.s.l., 1.IV.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (beating shrubs), 3♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19762); Same locality, koppie plateau, 30°46.198'S, 21°14.804'E, 1210 m a.s.l., 31.III.2025, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & M. Vickers (hand collecting), 1♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19754); Same locality, open plain grassland/thicket, 30°45.935'S, 21°16.345'E, 1120 m a.s.l., 30.III.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (sweeping grasses), 5♂ 1♀ (NMBA 19802); Same locality, open plain grassland/thicket, 30°45.935'S, 21°16.345'E, 1120 m a.s.l., 30.III.2025, leg. U.F.S. Entomology students (beating shrubs), 2♂ 2♀ (NMBA 19814); Namaqua National Park, Koeroebees, 30°08.683'S, 17°42.177'E, 240 m a.s.l., 14.I.2021,

leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (leaf litter, dry river bed), 1♀ (NCA 2021/723); Near Nigramoep, Skaaprivier Canyon, 29°33.130'S, 17°39.135'E, 690 m a.s.l., 10.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (beating shrubs, river bed), 1♂ 6♀ (NCA 2021/513); Nigramoep Slow Living Guest Farm, 29°31.869'S, 17°35.150'E, 745 m a.s.l., 9.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen, R. Christiaan & A. Stander (beating short shrubs, open plain), 1♂ 1♀ (NCA 2021/609); Richtersveld National Park, SE of Akkedis Pass, 28°11.123'S, 17°02.543'E, 535 m a.s.l., 7.VII.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & M. Vickers (beating short shrubs, dry river bed), 2♀ (NCA 2021/384); Same locality, Sendelingsdrif, Research Accommodation, 28°07.122'S, 16°53.480'E, 40 m a.s.l., 9.VII.2021, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booysen (hand collecting, at night on rocky outcrop), 1♂ (NCA 2021/186). Western Cape: Laingsburg district, Wagendrift Lodge, 33°22.861'S, 20°56.910'E, 520 m a.s.l., 22.I.2021, leg. C. Haddad, R. Booysen & A. Stander (hand collecting, under rocks in veld), 1♀ (NCA 2021/132).

DNA Barcodes: SPIZA579-21; SPIZA673-21; SPIZA674-21; SPIZA700-21; SPIZA826-21; SPIZA892-21; SPIZA893-21. Despite the slight variation in the shape of the epigynal ridges and dorsal RTA between the specimens sequenced (Figs 7–13), the genetic distance between them was less than 1% (Fig. 14), indicating that all these specimens are conspecific. In this analysis, specimens of many of the philodromid genera formed monophyletic groups (*Halodromus*, *Thanatus* and *Hirriusa*), although some others (*Tibellus*, *Gephyrota* and *Suemus*) were unresolved due to the low number of terminals or may be polyphyletic as currently composed (*Philodromus*).

FIGURE 14. Phylogenetic analysis of South African Philodromidae based on cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences, which were aligned using Muscle (Edgar 2004), with 200 bp sequence overlap. *Philodromus otjimbumbe* is marked in the orange rectangle and *Moggridgea* sp. (Migidae) was used as the out-group to root the tree.

Distribution: Widespread in western South Africa but in Namibia only recorded from the type locality in the north of the country (Fig. 15); it is thus likely widespread throughout Namibia too.

FIGURE 15. Distribution of *Philodromus otjimkumbe* in South Africa (white circles) and Namibia (star, type locality). Map produced on simplemappr.net.

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First records of *Poltys monstrosus* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Araneidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Poltys monstrosus* Simon, 1897, a species described from Sierra Leone, has for the first time been reported from Mozambique, Swaziland, Zimbabwe and South Africa. The species is recognised by the abdomen that are thick and broadly flattened at the top. They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Poltys* C.L. Koch, 1843 is represented by 42 species, of which nine are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). *Poltys* is a distinctive araneid genus recognised by a combination of widely separated lateral eyes and a pear-shaped carapace, where the “stalk” of the pear is an eye tubercle. Adult males are small and do not make webs, while the females are medium to large spiders. However, *Poltys* has an unexpectedly wide intra-specific variation in abdominal shape (Smith, 2003), suggesting that this plasticity may serve as a camouflage strategy against visually hunting predators like birds and wasps. In one group, the abdomens are rod-shaped and highly elongated, resembling twigs and in the other, the abdomens are thick and broadly flattened at the top, resembling dead buds, fruit or galls. The shape of the abdomen can vary among individuals within a species. Males are very small compared with females, and their abdomens are usually slightly extended oval.

They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn (Figs 1 & 2). The spiders are cryptically camouflaged, and during the day, they hide motionless on vegetation with their legs drawn tightly around their bodies (Fig. 6). Just the median eyes, which are situated on the anterior of the eye tubercle, are visible when they protrude between the legs. In this position, they often resemble part of a dead twig, a gall or a broken piece of wood.

Previously, only *Poltys furcifer* Simon, 1881, was known from South Africa. It is a species with a wide distribution across Africa. In 2014, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) identification service received a photo of a spider with a broad, flattened abdomen that could not be identified at that time. It was only in 2024 when a similar species was identified from material sampled from the Fountain Hill Estate in KwaZulu-Natal that it was recognized as a *Poltys* species. The specimen was compared with the descriptions of other African *Poltys* species, and it keyed out as *P. monstrosus* Simon, 1897.

The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

***Poltys monstrosus* Simon, 1897**

Poltys monstrosus Simon, 1897: 480 (Df)

Description: Female 10 mm. Body dull coloured, abdomen and legs densely covered with greyish-white setae (Fig. 2). Carapace pear-shaped; thoracic area with a very deep semicircular groove; ocular tubercle broad and obliquely inclined; carapace dark brown, smooth except for a broad band of setae stretching from fovea to eye region

Figures 1–2. *Poltys monstrosus*. 1. Female in orb web at Boesmansmond in the Eastern Cape (Mark Galpin). 2. Female in web at Blaauwberg Nature Reserve, Cape (Heather and Andrew Hodgson).

and clypeus (Fig. 3). Eyes: posterior lateral eyes are well separated from the anterior lateral eyes; median eyes closely grouped on anterior edge. Abdomen is large, barely longer than wide, covering the thoracic area; anterior margin rounded and furnished with rather small tubercles; three paired median tubercles are twinned,

Figures 3–5. *Poltys monstrosus*. 3–4. Female from Riebeeck West (Cecile Roux). 5. Female from Mbuluzi Game Reserve, Eswatini (Phil White).

with a few others slightly larger, and many small lateral tubercles toward the rear on both sides (Figs 4 & 5); adorned with somewhat irregular transverse zones, pale brownish-fawn in colour, covered with short, curved, dirty-white or yellowish hairs. Ventrally, pale brownish with the anterior region slightly darker. Legs with femora black with a bluish tint (Figs 4 & 5); the rest of the legs are densely covered with setae and are irregularly banded; four anterior tibiae are strongly curved, bearing long ventral spines in regular groups of four, and numerous irregular spines on the inner surface, which become shorter and denser toward the apex. *Poltys monstrosus* resemble the type species *P. illepidus* C.L. Koch, 1843, known from Japan to Australia.

LIFESTYLE

They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn. During the day they take up position on vegetation with the legs pulled very closely to the body, resembling part of a dead twig, a gall or a broken piece of bark (Figs 6 & 7).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique (iNat), Sierra Leone, Swaziland (iNat), South Africa (iNat) and Zimbabwe (iNat).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: (Fig. 8)

Figure 8. Distribution records of *Poltys monstrosus* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Poltys monstrosus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

Figures 6–7. *Poltys monstrosus* female from Cumberland Nature Reserve (Sunčana Bradley).

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The mushroom spider *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895) (Araneae: Theridiidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895), a species described from Transvaal, South Africa. It has since been recorded in Swaziland and in the provinces of KwaZulu-Natal, Eastern Cape, and Western Cape in South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

During surveys of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of theridiids were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), but due to a lack of taxonomic resolution, several species could not be identified. Between the sampled theridiid material, there were several specimens recognised as members of *Phoroncidia*. The genus *Phoroncidia* Westwood, 1835 is represented by 84 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Eleven species are known from Africa and three from South Africa.

One of the South African species sampled from the northern and central areas in South Africa keyed out as *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895). The female of *P. eburnea* was described as *Ulesanis eburnean* from Transvaal, no exact locality. That was some 130 years ago, and since then, little has been reported on the species. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Phoroncidia eburnea (Simon, 1895)

Ulesanis eburnea Simon, 1895: 147 (Df).

Phoroncidia eburnea Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 56;
Dippenaar-Schoeman. 2023: 139.

Description: Female TL 3 mm. Carapace fawn, margin darker; it is as wide as long; anterior blunt with eyes slightly protruding (Figs 2 & 11). Eyes: median eyes further from each other than from lateral eyes (Fig. 11); they occupy an area much wider than long, narrower in front than behind; eye field protrudes forward, overhanging the clypeus (Figs 5 & 10); median eyes larger than lateral eyes (Fig. 11). Sternum dark brown, somewhat smooth (Figs 13 & 14). Abdomen very large, completely overlapping the cephalothorax (Figs 1 & 7); broadly rounded with a very blunt uneven anterior margin (Figs 5–7); ivory-white above, densely and evenly sprinkled with small, round, brown spots, each bearing a tiny setae (Figs 16 & 17); in between with small pitted impressions (Fig. 8); on the posterior edge, with transverse folds forming dark stripes; ventrally dark (Figs 2, 13 & 14). Legs yellowish-brown (Figs 4 & 6). Only the female is known, but a smaller male was photographed at Kloof (Fig. 18).

Variation: The second author provided a series of *P. eburnean* images (Figs 2–6) taken at Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal. It shows how the shape of the abdomen varies from round (Fig. 2) to having a central dorsal hump (Figs. 5–7). The colour of the specimens varies from creamy white to fawn (Figs 4 & 7), with the hump sometimes having a darker tint.

Figures 1–10. *Phoroncidia eburnea*. 1. Female from Delmas. 2–7. Images of specimens photographed at Kloof. 8. Female from Rayton. 8–9. Egg sacs of *P. eburnean*. Credits: 1 & 9. Peter Webb. 2–7 & 9–10. Bruce Blake.

LIFESTYLE

Phoroncidia eburnea is very small and not easily seen. During SANSA surveys, they were sampled by sweeping and beating the vegetation. Research on members of *Phoroncidia* showed that they hunt at night and their webs consist of a single, horizontal sticky silk thread. At Kloof in South Africa, strange egg sacs were observed, always with *P. eburnea* in the vicinity (Figs 9 & 10).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa (Fig. 29).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Ongeluksnek (-30.55, 28.57); Prentjies-berg (-31.18, 28.28); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Gauteng:** Rayton (-25.74, 28.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Garden Castle (-29.75, 29.2); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Kruger National Park: Mopani Tsendze (-23.685, 31.518); Kruger National Park: Pretoriuskop Numbi (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park: Pretoriuskop Shabeni (-25.12, 31.237); Kruger National Park: Satara (-24.399, 31.736); Kruger National Park: Satara (-24.405, 31.766); Kruger National Park: Satara N'wanetsi (-24.448, 31.865); Delmas (-26.146, 28.683). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.678, 24.304); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Tswalu Nature Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

Figure 19. Distribution records of *Phoroncidia eburnea* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Phoroncidia eburnea* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

Figures 16–18. *Phoroncidia eburnea*. 16. Female dorsal view. 17. Close up showing the texture and setae on abdomen. Undescribed male from Kloof. Credits: Peter Webb.

HABITAT

Rare spider sampled when sweeping low vegetation. This species has been sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Although only the female is known, the species has a fairly wide distribution and is protected in Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2008) and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018). Males have been collected but still need to be described (Fig. 18).

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More on the red spider *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 (Araneae: Theridiidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 a species that was described from the Cape Flat, Cape Peninsula, South Africa some 121 years ago. The species has now a wider distribution and has been recorded from seven provinces. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

A female of *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 was first recorded and described from the Cape Flat, Cape Peninsula, South Africa, some 121 years ago. Since then, nothing has been reported on the species. During surveys of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of theridiids were sampled, but unfortunately, due to a lack of taxonomic revision, numerous species could not be identified (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2025).

Between the SANSA samples, there were numerous theridiid specimens recognized by their bright red colour. In search of a species name, the only red theridiid found in the literature belongs to the genus *Rubrorridion* Wunderlich, 2011, with the type species *Theridion musivum* Simon, 1898 (Vanuytven, 2021). However, the somatic features of *R. musivum* differ from the specimens sampled in South Africa in several characters. Unfortunately, this striking red colour fades in specimens preserved in alcohol. This warrants a reexamination of the *Theridion* species described from South Africa, not only focusing on the red body colour.

The somatic characters and drawings of a South African endemic species described by O.P.-Cambridge (1904) from Constantia Flats in the Western Cape correspond with this spider. Outstanding characters are the large, almost globular, orange-yellow abdomen (in alcohol) that partly covers the carapace. The abdomen is marked faintly with a white longitudinal central line with 2-3 slightly oblique lines on each side. The lines on the abdomen are formed by minute white spots (O.P.-Cambridge, 1904). He also stated that it is possible that other specimens, when found, will exhibit some modification in colour and markings. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Theridion delicatum O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904

Theridion delicatum O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904: 157;
Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 29.

Description: Female as described by Pickard-Cambridge (1904) from alcohol material. Cephalothorax pale yellowish white. Eyes in two rows, nearly equal in size (Fig. 5); eyes on black spots; eyes in two rows of equal length; anterior row slightly recurved and posterior row slightly procurved; median ocular quadrangle form a square (Figs 3 & 5); clypeus wide; chelicerae moderate long; sternum round broadly truncated posteriorly; few longish bristles on the caput directed forwards; the longest setae in a transverse line at the middle of the central quadrangle.

Figure 1–3. *Theridion delicatum*. 1. Female from Ferncliff near Boulder Dam (Alan Manson). 2. Female from Paarl (Cecile Roux) 3. Female from Rayton (Peter Webb).

Figures 4–11. *Theridion delicatum*. 4–7. Line drawings. 4. Body lateral view. 5. Eye pattern. 6. Epigyne. 7. Female habitus clearly showing the setae on the abdomen. 8. Showing the colour in a live specimen. 9. Compared to specimen from alcohol. 10. Eye pattern. 11. Female epigyne. Credits: 4–7. After Pickard-Cambridge (1904). 8. Linda Wiese. 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 10–11. Peter Webb.

Abdomen large, almost globular; projecting largely over the carapace (Fig. 4); in alcohol a dull orange-yellow marked faintly with a white longitudinal central line (Fig. 9); two or three horizontal short lines on each side of central line and forming a band around the anterior edge; lines on abdomen formed by minute white spots; dorsum with numerous long backwards directed setae (Fig. 1). Legs moderately long; 1423 slender; furnished with fine setae and slender bristles; same colour as cephalothorax; femora and tibiae of leg IV dark and as also less strongly those of the other legs (Figs 7 & 8). Male undescribed.

VARIATION: In live specimens the body and legs are usually red (Figs 1–3). The carapace is red with only the eyes on black spots (Fig. 10). The abdomen colour varies from a uniform red in some specimens (Fig. 12), while in others the abdomen is decorated with white lines (Figs 8, 13, 21). In some, there are dark bands present on both sides of the median white band (Figs 14 & 15). The colour of the legs varies from red with no dark bands to red with only leg IV banded (Fig. 3) or red with all the femora dark (Fig. 12) to almost completely black legs (Figs 16 & 17).

LIFESTYLE

They do not make a web and run around on the plants and ground. With their small size and red colour they resemble some of the Erythraeidae mites (Figs 18–19). The egg sac is covered by an uneven layer of silk and seems to be carried around by the female (Fig. 16). Fig. 16 show a male and female busy to mate.

Figures 12–21 *Theridion delicatum*. 13. Female from Wynford (Peter Webb). 13. Female from Riebeeck West (Cecile Rouw). 14. Female from Loskopdam (Peter Webb). 15. Female from East Londen (Simon and Eunete Van Wyk-Schumacher). 16. Mating (Simon and Eunete Van Wyk-Schumacher). 17. Female with egg sac (Linda Wiese). 18–21. Mites species resembling *T. delicatum* (Peter Webb).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Zimbabwe (iNat).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 22)

Figure 22. Distribution records of *Theridion delicatum* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Theridion delicatum* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

DISCUSSION

When the African *Theridion* species are eventually revised this species may be placed in a new genus or it might be a new species in *Rubroridion*.

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The Komaggas palp footed spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910 from South Africa (Araneae: Palpimanidae)

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ABSTRACT: The spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910 was described from Komaggas in the Northern Cape in 1910. In the first spider atlas of 2010, it was still only known from the type locality. Since then, it has been recorded during surveys undertaken in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve in 2013 and surveys in the Richtersveld National Park. The type material of the species in the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (Germany) was re-examined in 2019, and more information became available. The general morphology of the species is provided based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

The Palpimanidae is a spider family assigned to 20 genera (World Spider Catalog, 2025). *Palpimanus* Dufour, 1820 is the second largest genus in the family, with 43 species currently known from the West Palearctic, Africa and South America. To date, 21 species of *Palpimanus* are known to occur in Africa, south of the Sahara and 14 from South Africa. The African species have not yet been revised except that the type material of four species in the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (Germany) was redescribed by Zonstein & Marusik (2019).

One of the four was the spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910, that was described from Komaggas in the Northern Cape in 1910. Little is known about the species, and in the first spider atlas of 2010, it was still only known from the type locality. The species has been recorded during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2018) in 2013 and surveys in the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.* 2025). More information on the species became available with the publication of Zonstein & Marusik (2019) and several specimens on iNaturalist have been recognised.

The general morphology of the species is provided based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Palpimanus paroculus Simon, 1910

Palpimanus paroculus Simon, 1910: 179; Griffin and Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991: 158; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 18; Zonstein & Marusik 2019: 89.

Diagnosis: Female total length: 5 mm. Cephalothorax: dark purple, densely granulated and covered with long, ash-white setae (Fig. 1). Anterior eyes are small, equal in size, and arranged in a slightly curved line (Fig. 2). The median eyes are distinctly farther from the lateral eyes than the lateral eyes are from each other. Posterior eyes minute, forming a perfectly straight line when viewed from above; the median eyes are farther from the lateral eyes than the lateral eyes are from each other, with the interocular space at least three times wider than the diameter of an eye. Median eye area: more than three times longer than wide, and much narrower in front than behind. Abdomen brick-coloured, densely covered with ash-white pubescence (Fig. 3); the epigastric region is somewhat hardened, posteriorly almost straightly truncated, anteriorly black and wrinkled, strongly transversely striated toward the pedicel.

Figures 1–3. *Palpimanus paroculus* female. 1. Dorsal view. 2. Anterior view. 3. Female with an egg sac. Credits: 1. Cecile Roux. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Chelicerae and sternum dark. Anterior legs thick, reddish-chestnut to nearly black. Remaining legs dark tawny-reddish, with femora slightly lighter in colour. Epigyne with an broad epigynal scutum (Fig. 4). Male unknown.

LIFESTYLE

The species is a free-living ground dweller and it has been recorded from the more arid Desert, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo Biomes. In the Tswalu Game Reserve, a female with an egg sac was photographed (Fig. 6-8). The female deposited the round white egg sac in a retreat made of small stones and plant material held together by silk threads. The provided some protection for the eggs. At Richtersveld National Park, six specimens were hand collected from leaf litter (Haddad *et al.*, 2025).

DISTRIBUTION

The distribution of *P. paroculus* is shown in Fig. 13. Simon (1910) described the first female from Kommagas (then Kammagas) in the Namakwa District Municipality, Northern Cape.

During surveys of SANSA, it was sampled from the Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018) and from the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2025), both from the Northern Cape. In the World Spider Catalog (2025), the species is also listed from Namibia. However, Griffin and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991) stated that there are no confirmed published records from Namibia, and they only refer to Simon (1910) with a record from South Africa.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa (Fig. 13).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Lectotype *Northern Cape Province*, Komaggas (original “Kammagas”)(-29.75, 17.4). SANSA surveys: Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Richtersveld National Park (-28.25, 17.17)

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Figure 13. Distribution records of *Palpimanus paroculus* in South Africa. Showing the type locality, the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Palpimanus paroculus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

Figures 6–12. *Palpimanus paroculus*. 6–8. Female busy constructing retreat for egg sac. 9. Juvenile. 10. Epigastral scutum. 11–12. Adult females showing the variation in abdomen colour. Credits: 6–8, 11. Peter Webb. 9 & 12. Cecile Roux. 10. Charles Haddad.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The status of the species remains obscure. It is presently only known from the Northern Cape Province. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons. However the species received some protection in the following protected areas: Meerkat National Park, Richtersveld National Park, Tswalu Kalahari Reserve and Witsand Nature Reserve.

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Observation on the arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* (Pocock, 1900) in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: The arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* (Pocock, 1900) is an endemic South African species. It was originally described from Port Elizabeth in the Eastern Cape 125 years ago. Since then, very little has been discussed. The general morphology of the species based on photographs of live specimens is discussed. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status and threats are provided.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parapalystes* erected by Croeser (1996) is represented by five species endemics to South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Croeser revised *Palystes* in 1996 and erected the genus *Parapalystes*, with *Parapalystes euphorbiae* from the north-western Cape as the type species. He transferred four *Palystes* species to *Parapalystes*: *P. cultrifer* (Pocock, 1900), described from Grahamstown; *P. lycosinus* Pocock, 1900, from Port Elizabeth; *Ocypete megacephala* C.L. Koch, 1845, from Cape of Good Hope; and *P. whiteae* Pocock, 1902, also from Grahamstown.

Members of *Parapalystes* resemble *Palystes* with respect to eye arrangement and general body shape and posture, and they usually have a white band on the clypeal edge. However, they differ from *Palystes* in the following aspects: the cephalic region of the carapace is domed posterior to the posterior eye row and is dorsally decorated by two fine white lines, which are thinly divided, from the middle posterior eye row to the white patch immediately anterior to the fovea. The sternum is black except for a white to yellow pattern on the anterior third in some species. The abdomen has a distinct heart mark, and the leg coxae have two to five round black marks ventrally, and there are distinct genital differences between the species (Croeser, 1996).

In this paper, we revisit the arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* that was described by Pocock 125 years ago. Very little is known about the species, and in the first spider atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), the species was known only from one additional locality, the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). During the South African National Surveys of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015), the species was also sampled from the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) and six other localities in both the Eastern and Western Cape provinces, as listed in the Sparassidae Photo Identification guide (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). In this paper, we make all information on *P. lycosinus* available. Unfortunately, the original description of the species lacks detail. Nothing has been added except for the images of the genitalia provided by Jäger & Kunz (2005).

METHODS

Specimens collected during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) surveys were deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

Figures 1–3. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 1. Female from Kammanassie Nature Reserve, dorsal view. 2–3. Female from Namakwa District. Dorsal view (2) and ventral view (3). Credits: 1. Felix Riegel. 2–3. Cecile Roux.

Figures 4–7. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 4–5. Anterior and dorsal views of carapace. 4. Showing the white band between the anterior and posterior eye row. 5. Showing the white line present from the middle posterior eye row to the white patch immediately anterior to the fovea. 6. Eye pattern. 7. Male palp. Credits: 4–5. Cecile Roux. 6–7. After Jäger & Kunz (2005).

TAXONOMY

Palystes lycosinus Pocock, 1900

Parapalystes lycosinus Pocock, 1900: 330; Croeser, 1996: 90 (designated male lectotype and female and subadult paralectotypes); Jäger & Kunz, 2005: 168; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 927; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 61; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2024: 234.

Diagnosis: Total length 21 mm. Carapace as wide as long posteriorly evenly rounded (Figs 1 & 14); cephalic region posterior of eyes with a slight dome (Fig. 5). Carapace dark cover with a layer of setae that vary in colour from grey, fawn to white giving the carapace a mottled appearance (Fig. 5); a band of white setae present between the anterior and posterior eye rows (Fig. 4); a narrow white band originating between the posterior median eyes extend posteriorly to the fovea where it broaden and is surrounded on both sides by two dark triangular patches (Fig. 5); dark striae present originating from the fovea (Fig. 1); chelicerae are brownish-gray with a slightly darker terminal segment (Fig. 4); white band on clypeus absent with band fawn setae; sternum black (Fig. 3). The coxae are brownish gray dorsally and pale ochre-yellow on the underside, with brown tiger-like spot (Fig. 3). Legs dorsally same colour as carapace with mottled appearance; femora ventrally dark decorated with numerous small pale spots (Fig. 4); tibiae ventrally with dark and white bands (Fig. 3). Metatarsus and tarsus with dense scopulae (Fig. 15). Abdomen long oval; dorsum covered by setae layer with colour varying from fawn, grey to brownish; mid-line decorated with 3-5 paired triangular patches arranged in longitudinal line. Ventrally fawn to reddish brown with dark spots; two dark patches varying in shape and size are present below the epigynal groove and in front of the spinnerets (Figs 3, 11–13). Tibia of male palp armed at its distal end above with a single, slightly sinuous, basally stout, apically pointed spur directed forwards and outwards over the base of the tarsus (Fig. 7).

LIFESTYLE

Parapalystes lycosinus is a free-living wandering ground spider sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo in the Eastern, Northern and Western Cape. They were sampled with pitfall traps and most of the records from iNaturalist show them on rocky areas. The female deposits the white egg sac on the ground under rocks, while she stays in proximity to provide protection.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution and are known from three provinces. It is protected in the Eastern Cape in the Addo National Park, Fort Fordyce Forest Reserve and Commando Drift Nature Reserve. In the Western Cape it is known from the Karoo National Park (Pettersvlei) and Aardvark Nature Reserve and Kammanassie Nature Reserve.

Figures 8–16. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 8–10. Abdomens dorsal view showing the variation. 11–13. Abdomen ventral view. 14–16. Habitus showing the colour variations. Credits: 10 & 14. Cecile Roux, Peter Webb and Felix Riegel. 11.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Fig. 17)

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Figure 17. Distribution records of *Parapalystes lycosinus* in South Africa. Showing the SANSa distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist "Research Grade" observations of *Parapalystes lycosinus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

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Spider diversity in a native grassland fragment in Irene, in the Gauteng Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last few years. Over a period of six years, spiders were regularly collected and photographed in a native grassland patch near Irene in the Gauteng Province, South Africa. It is home to a diverse group of spiders, and 39 spider families represented by 150 genera and 257 species have been collected. The Araneidae (46) Salticidae (36 spp.), and Thomisidae (32 spp.) are the most species-rich families. Several of the species collected are new to science or first records for Gauteng. All species collected have been photographed, and this has added a valuable contribution to the South African National Survey of Arachnida Virtual Museum and iNaturalist. It is important that pristine areas like this in urban areas be protected and not developed.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The increasing growth of the urban population is one of the main challenges of this century. The role of cities in the loss and degradation of global biodiversity was already recognised at the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in 1992. Whilst cities pose major challenges for protecting biodiversity, the opportunities they offer to protect invertebrate biodiversity have largely been ignored. These areas, although fragmented, can serve an important ecological function and require proper management and conservation. Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 10-15 years, especially in Europe and North America (Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Frazer & Frankie, 1986).

In South Africa, only a handful of urban surveys have been carried out since the end of the last century. Most of these surveys were undertaken in national gardens and small reserves within the boundaries of cities. Tucker (1920) was the first to report on the spiders of the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden in the Western Cape. Follow-up surveys in the Western Cape were mainly undertaken on the Table Mountain (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024) and Kirstenbosch (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Clark & Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanic garden in Pietermaritzburg, KwaZulu-Natal and spiders from road islands in Durban (Whitmore *et al.*, 2002). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country. In the Free State, surveys were undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). From Gauteng, a three-year survey at the Rietondale Research Station in Pretoria was reported on by Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Also from Pretoria, there are checklists of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022a), the Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and the Pretoria National Botanical Garden (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

The only survey in a home garden was undertaken in the Eastern Cape at Jeffreys Bay, where 151 species were recorded (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). We report here on the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS) carried out in the pristine grassland fragment near the Irene Village, Centurion, in the Gauteng Province of South Africa (Figs 1-3). The province falls within both the Savanna and the highly threatened Grassland Biome, and approximately 83% of the province comprises Highveld Grassland vegetation types, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa.

We present a comprehensive checklist of spiders sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS) and include information on the species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status.

Figures 1–3. The native grassland fragment sampled in Irene in the Gauteng Province, South Africa during the Irene Grassland Survey. Credits: Peter Webb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The second author (PW) first visited this small, pristine grassland area bordering Irene in 2013 and sampled numerous interesting invertebrates. He decided to survey the area on a regular basis as part of SANSa Grassland surveys and it was known as the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS). Although it was not conceived as a scientific study as such, the result of observations and sampling undertaken over a six-year period resulted in several new records and 257 spider species sampled.

Study area: The small hectare pristine grassland area of the small village of Irene (25° 53'29.81" S 28°14'04.62" E) in Centurion, South Africa, is approximately 1 km² in size at an altitude of 1465 m a.s.l. (Fig. 4). The western boundary appears to be a little disturbed with alien weed and houses on its border (Figs 1-2, 4). The area is burnt on an annual basis, usually around July.

The area is on dolomite and is a haven for many different species of grass with an abundance of wildflowers in the spring. Although trees are sparse, the odd Buffalo thorn (*Ziziphus mucronata*), white stinkwood (*Celtis africana*), dogwood (*Rhamnus prinoides*), karee, taaibos, and *Grewia flava* make it very typical of Highveld grassland (Fig. 3). The following grasses have been recognised: Heart-seed love grass (*Eragrostis capensis*); Natal Red-Tops (*Melinis repens*); Common Finger Grass (*Digitaria eriantha*); Velvet Signal Grass (*Brachiaria serrata*); Red Grass (*Themeda triandra*), and Hairy trident Grass (*Tristachya leucothrix*) (Figs 1–3, 5–8).

Study period and methods: This checklist is the result of spider collecting carried out using different techniques over different time periods. Most of the collecting was by hand but also included occasional use of sweep netting and pitfall traps. The arachnids were identified by the first author (ASD). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria.

Photography: The spiders were photographed, some in the field and others in a studio in Irene using a Nikon D200 camera body with a Nikon 105mm macro lens coupled with an R1 wireless flash kit by PW. The photographs could be viewed on the iNaturalist dataset.

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020), where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range of the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within the categories: Data Deficient (DD) and Least Concern (LC) (Table 3).

TABLE 1. Results of four Gauteng Urban Area Survey project of SANSa undertaken in Pretoria urban areas, listing the total number of families and species and the three most species rich families recorded.

LOCALITY	SPP.	FAM	ABUNDANT FAMILIES			REFERENCES
FAERIE GLEN NATURE RESERVE	103	31	Salticidae (17)	Araneidae (12)	Thomisidae (11)	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022e
GROENKLOOF NATURE RESERVE	112	35	Salticidae (20)	Gnaphosidae (12)	Lycosidae (11)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2023
IRENE GRASSLAND	257	39	Araneidae (46)	Salticidae (36)	Thomisidae (32)	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb
PRETORIA NATIONAL BOT. GARDEN	152	36	Araneidae (23)	Salticidae (21)	Thomisidae (14)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2024

Figure 4. The yellow block show the area sampled in Irene.

Figures 5–8. Showing the field type and the different grass species sampled during the Irene Grassland survey. Credit: Peter Webb

Endemicity value: The global distribution of each species obtained from literature and the World Spider Catalog was provided to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 3). Values used to indicate species endemicity (E): 6 – only known from the type locality (Irene); 5 – known from several localities in the Gauteng (GE); 4 – known from Gauteng as well as an adjacent province; 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE); 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE); 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

RESULTS

Numbers present: A total of 257 species, 152 genera, from 39 families, were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). The IGS formed part of the Gauteng Urban Area Survey project of SANSa in Pretoria, where several surveys have been undertaken (Table 1). The first survey dealt with the spider diversity of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022e), where 103 species were recorded, followed by 112 species from the Groenkloof Nature Reserve and 152 species from the Pretoria National Botanical Garden. The 257 van Irene is 100 species more than the Groenkloof survey. This could be attributed to the longer sampling period in Irene. Owen (2010) emphasized the importance of ongoing long-term monitoring when assessing the diversity of even small areas, particularly for invertebrates whose populations often exhibit significant inter-seasonal and inter-annual fluctuations.

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of the Irene Grassland Survey, Gauteng with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.) sampled

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	%	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	%
Agelenidae	3	3	1.2	Philodromidae	5	9	3.5
Araneidae	22	46	17.9	Pholcidae	3	3	1.2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	3	1.2	Phyxelididae	1	1	0.4
Clubionidae	1	2	0.8	Pisauridae	3	5	1.9
Corinnidae	4	4	1.6	Prodidomidae	2	3	1.3
Cyrtachenidae	1	3	1.2	Salticidae	21	36	14.
Deinopidae	1	1	0.4	Scytodidae	1	2	0.8
Dictynidae	1	1	0.4	Segestriidae	1	1	0.4
Eresidae	1	1	0.4	Selenopidae	1	2	0.8
Gnaphosidae	17	21	8.2	Sparassidae	2	2	0.8
Hersiliidae	1	1	0.4	Stasimopidae	1	1	0.4
Idiopidae	1	3	1.3	Tetragnathidae	1	3	1.3
Linyphiidae	3	3	1.3	Theraphosidae	1	1	0.4
Liocranidae	1	1	0.4	Theridiidae	9	14	5.8
Lycosidae	10	18	7.0	Thomisidae	12	32	12.5
Macrobnidae	1	1	0.4	Trachelidae	4	4	1.6
Oecobiidae	1	1	0.4	Trochenteridae	1	1	0.4
Oonopidae	1	1	0.4	Uloboridae	2	2	0.8
Oxyopidae	3	13	5.1	Zodariidae	5	5	1.9
Palpimanidae	1	2	0.8	39 families	152	257	

Family diversity: Of the 39 spider families collected (Tables 2 & 5), the three most species-rich families are the Araneidae (46 spp.), Salticidae (36 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (32 spp.). Thirteen families are represented by singletons.

The Salticidae, with 36 species, was the family with the highest number of species recorded from the four surveys in Pretoria, with the number ranges between 17 and 36 species (Table 1). All the Salticidae species of Irene were identified to species level and they are all listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

The Araneidae was the most species-rich family in two of the Pretoria sites, with numbers ranging between 23 and 46 (Table 1). Several interesting Araneidae species have been recorded from Irene. Six species that could not be identified to species level are possibly new records for South Africa (Figs 9a-f), and five species were first records from South Africa and 12 first records for Gauteng (Table 3; Figs 10a-d; 11-14).

Figure 9 (a-f). Some of the undetermined Araneidae species recorded from Irene.

Figure 10 (a-d). Araneidae species from Irene recorded for the first time from South Africa and Gauteng.

The Thomisidae was the third species-rich family recorded from the three Pretoria sites, with numbers ranging from 11 to 32 species as recorded from Irene (Table 1). All the thomisids were identified to species level and they are all listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

Specimens sampled during this 6-year survey were regularly photographed and more than a 1000 photographs became available. With series of photographs on species available we were able to publish several papers on new records and the behaviour of species such as *Ammoxenus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2024a (Fig. 26) and *Hogna* spp. (Fig. 27). Specimens also form part of generic revisions (Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013 (Table 3; Figs 18 & 19).

TABLE 3: Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey that were first records for Gauteng and South Africa.

SPECIES	FIRST RECORD	REFERENCE
ARANEIDAE		
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (Fig. 10a)
<i>Argiope tapinobata</i> Bjørn, 1997	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022a (Fig. 11)
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (Fig. 10b)
<i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022a (Fig. 10c)
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022b (Fig. 16)
<i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022b (Fig. 17)
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022c (Fig. 10d)
CORINNIIDAE		
<i>Apochinomma elongata</i> Haddad, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2022 (Fig. 12)
LYCOSIDAE		
<i>Pardosa schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , (Fig. 19)
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , (Fig. 20)
MACROBUNIDAE		
<i>Elelies limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022 f (Fig. 13)
THERIDIIDAE		
<i>Latrodectus pallidus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1872	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022d (Fig. 14)
THOMISIDAE		
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020a (Fig. 18)
<i>Heriaeus peterwebbi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> 2020a (Fig. 19)
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020b (Fig. 22)
<i>Synema marlothi</i> Dahl, 1907	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 23)
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 24)
TETRAGNATHIDAE		
<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 25)

TABLE 4: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey, Gauteng.

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	19	7.4
Data deficient DD	3	1.2
Least concern LC	235	91.4
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	23	8.9
1 – African endemics (AE)	111	43.2
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	50	19.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	52	20.2
4 – South African endemics (SAE):	0	0
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	2	0.8
6 – Type locality	0	0

Argiope tapinobata

Apochinomma elongatum

Elelies limpopo

Latrodectus pallidus

Heliophanus africanus

Figures 11-15. Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey. For more information on the species see Table 3.

Endemism: Twenty-three species (8.9%) sampled at Irene have a distribution wider than Africa, while 111 species (43.2%) are African endemics (AE), 50 species (20.2%) are Southern African endemics, and 54 species (21%) are South African endemics (Table 4). Only two species was endemic to Gauteng a Stasimopidae trapdoor spider *Stasimopus robertsi* Hewitt, 1910 and a Salticidae *Heliophanus africanus* Wesotowska, 1986 (Fig. 15).

Conservation status: Nineteen species were not evaluated and two species: *Nemoscolus obscurus* Simon, 1897, *Cheiracanthium dippenaarae* Lotz, 2007 were listed as Data Deficient. The rest of the 235 species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

Descriptive studies in the United Kingdom suggest that gardens, both urban and otherwise, can harbour a considerable diversity of spider species (Dawson, 2003; Gurr, 1968; Russell-Smith, 2002a; Thomas, 2002; , Owen, 2010). Numbers of species recorded in the 10 gardens included in these reports ranged from 23 to 113, representing from 3% to 17% of the British spider fauna.

Gauteng, the smallest of South Africa's nine provinces, is rich in biodiversity. During SANSA surveys 461 spider species have been recorded (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The 257 species recorded from IGS represent 55.7% of the Gauteng fauna. Yet it is also the most densely populated province and thus faces significant development pressures. It is the most densely populated province in the country with the highest population growth rate and the demand for urban land in this rapidly urbanizing province is therefore high.

CONCLUSION

From these surveys, it has become clear that gaps in our knowledge of the grasslands of Gauteng still exist, especially regarding the urban and suburban areas (Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Although Gauteng is the smallest province in South Africa, it is characterized by high biodiversity. Consequently, the biodiversity in the province is highly threatened by industrialization, mining, agriculture, and especially urbanization, the latter due to the current high demands for the provision of land and basic services to alleviate poor living conditions. Essentially, the successful conservation of biodiversity within Gauteng will require the identification of priority areas where development habitat transformation and fragmentation should be discouraged and conservation efforts should be focused.

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Nemoscolus cotti

Neoscona kivuensis

Heriaeus copricola

Heriaeus peterwebbi

Pardosa schreineri

Zenonina albocaudata

Synema decens

Synema marlothi

Synema simoneae

Leucauge auronotum

Ammoxenus amphalodes

Hogna spenceri

Oxyopes sp. (undetermined)

Oxyopes sp. (undetermined)

Figures 16-28. Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey. For more information on the species see Table 3

TABLE 5: Spiders of Irene Grassland Survey listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND) LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered.

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
1. AGELENIDAE				3. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Agelena</i> sp. 1		NE		<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Cheiracanthium dippenaarae</i> Lotz, 2007	3	DD	SAE
<i>Olorunia punctata</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
2. ARANEIDAE				4. CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Araneus</i> sp. 1 (Fig. 9a)		NE		<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	3	LC	SAE	<i>Clubiona pupillaris</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	5. CORINNIDAE			
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C	<i>Apochinomma elongata</i> Haddad, 2013	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope tapinobata</i> Björn, 1997	1	LC	AE	<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Messapus martini</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	6. CYRTAUCHENIIDAE			
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa nigriceps</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C. L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	7. DEINOPIDAE			
<i>Hypsosinga pygmaea</i> (Sundevall, 1831)	1	LC	AE	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hypsosinga</i> sp. 2 (new) (Fig. 9b)		NE		8. DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Hypsosinga</i> sp. 3 (new) (Fig. 9c)		NE		<i>Archaedictyna conducta</i> (O.P.- Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	9. ERESIDAE			
<i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	2	LC	STHE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
<i>Isoxya mucronata</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE	10. GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Larinioides</i> sp. (undetermined) (Fig. 9f)		NE		<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	<i>Drassodes bechuanicus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus obscurus</i> Simon, 1897	3	DD	SAE	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus</i> sp. (new) (Fig. 9d)		NE		<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
<i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986	1	LC	AE	<i>Smionia lineatipes</i> (Purcell, 1908)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus biplagiatus</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	0	LC	C	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	11. HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Prasonica nigrotaeniata</i> (Simon, 1909)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	12. IDIOPIDAE			
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	<i>Idiops fryi</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ursa</i> sp. 2 (new) (Fig. 9e)		NE					

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
13. LINYPHIIDAE				22. PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE	<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Limoneta sirimoni</i> (Bosmans, 1979)	2	LC	AE	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE	<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
14. LIOCRANIDAE				<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	<i>Tibitanus sexmaculatus</i> Simon, 1907	1	LC	AE
15. LYCOSIDAE				23. PHYXELIDIDAE			
<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
<i>Amblyothele ecologica</i> Russell-Smith, Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2009	3	LC	SAE	<i>Spermophora</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	24. PISAURIDAE			
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE	<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Cispus variegatus</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Euprostenops bayaonianus</i> (Brito Capello, 1867)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna zuluana</i> Roewer, 1959	3	LC	SAE	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	25. PRODIDOMIDAE			
<i>Pardosa schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	<i>Eleleis limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Theuma parva</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa hirsuta</i> (Russell-Smith, 1981)	2	LC	STHE	26. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Trabea heterocolata</i> Strand, 1913	1	LC	AE	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trabea ornatipalpis</i> Russell-Smith, 1982	3	LC	SAE	<i>Dendryphantes silvestris</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE	<i>Evarcha vittula</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
16. MACROBUNIDAE				<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE
<i>Chresiona</i> sp.		NE		<i>Hasarius adansonii</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
17. OECOBIIDAE				<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
18. OONOPIIDAE				<i>Heliocapensis charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gamasomorpha australis</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE	<i>Heliophanus africanus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	5	DD	SAE
19. OXYOPIIDAE				<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Kima atra</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Helafricanus pistaciae</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne uvira</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1917	1	LC	AE	<i>Neaetha bulawayoensis</i> (Wesolowska, 2000)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3 (green)		NE		<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesolowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 9 (black)		NE		<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 10 (velvet)		NE		<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
20. PALPIMANIDAE				<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Palpimanus</i> sp. 2 (immature)		NE		<i>Thyene aperta</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
21. PHILODROMIDAE				<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE				
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE				
<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE				
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE				

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus deamatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trapezocephalus infaustus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus lesserti</i> (Wesołowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus orchestra</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus transvaalicus</i> (Simon, 1901)	3	LC	SAE
27. SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Scytodes thoracica</i> (Latreille, 1802)	0	LC	C
28. SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
29. SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Anyphops lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
30. SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
31. STASIMOPIDAE			
<i>Stasimopus robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1910	5	LC	SAE
32. TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge argyrescens</i> Benoit, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
33. THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
34. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
<i>Dipoena</i> sp. 1		NE	
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus pallidus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1872	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907			
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3		NE	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 7		NE	
<i>Tidarren</i> sp. 1		NE	
35. THOMISIDAE			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heriaeus peterwebbi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses fuscus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pactactes obesus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema marlothi</i> Dahl, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
36. TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE
<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
<i>Spinotrachelas</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
37. TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
38. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
39. ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Microdiores</i> sp. 1		NE	
<i>Ranops robinae</i> Jocqué & Henrard, 2020	3	LC	SAE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE